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A CASE STUDY- IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON THE EDUCATION SYSTEM OF INDIA VS FINLAND

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ABSTRACT

This study describes the situation under which India and Finland were during the pandemic. The researchers have done a systematic analysis based on secondary data on how the government tackled the covid-19 pandemic in terms of all educational endeavors. After going through the reliable secondary literature it was found that because of a lack of recourse and awareness both from parents and students the quality of education has undergone a significant decline. whereas on the contrary Finland sustained its education system notwithstanding the pandemic was due to its literacy rate, adoption of digital learning, Fostering the parents, and acknowledgment among parents of the catastrophic situation. Finns were ready to beat the heat of covid- 19 as Finland was able to make the switch from face-to-face instruction to distant learning and back again because of many factors. It was a predetermined response from their side to properly serve the well-being of children, the Finns have a stance on education and learning that frequently defies popular knowledge such as caring less about children's standardized performance and teachers' responsibility. Hence further it was concluded that similar measures can be employed to overcome such a phenomenon.

Keywords- Pandemic, Education System, quality Education, Digital Learning, literacy.

INTRODUCTION

As the world becomes increasingly interconnected, so do the risks we face. The COVID-19 pandemic has not stopped at national borders. It has affected people regardless of nationality, level of education, income, or gender. But the same has not been true for its consequences, which have hit the most vulnerable hardest. Education is no exception. Students from privileged backgrounds, supported by their parents and eager and able to learn, could find their way past closed school doors to alternative learning opportunities. Those from disadvantaged backgrounds often remained shut out when their schools shut down. This crisis has exposed the many inadequacies and inequities in our education systems – from access to the broadband and computers needed for online education, and the supportive environments needed to focus on learning, up to the misalignment between resources and needs. The lockdowns in response to COVID-19 have interrupted conventional schooling with nationwide school closures in most OECD and partner countries, the majority lasting at least 10 weeks. While the educational community has made concerted efforts to maintain learning continuity during this period, children and students have had to rely more on their resources to continue learning remotely through the Internet, television, or radio. Teachers also had to adapt to new pedagogical concepts and modes of delivery of teaching, for which they may not have been trained. In particular, learners in the most marginalized groups, who don't have access to digital learning resources or lack the resilience and engagement to learn on their own, are at risk of falling behind.

METHODOLOGY

For the proposed purpose of the study, the researchers have collected secondary data through the data provided on the Internet.

DETERIORATION OF INDIAN EDUCATION QUALITY

No one expected a virus-like Covid-19 to arrive and change the lives of individuals without distinction. It took some time for everyone to adapt to the new normal that was brought about by Covid-19. Schools and other educational facilities were shut down as a consequence of the Covid-19 effect. Covid-19's initial effect was mitigated in most countries by temporarily closing schools. It was reopened for a few grades and then closed again, which raised infection rates.

School is closed, but children may still access educational resources like online classrooms and radio programs even while the schools are closed. Even while it's a positive development, many students who lack the financial means to take advantage of online education are left behind. Many students are having difficulty obtaining the necessary technology to participate in online education. Digital teaching is new to teachers who are specialists in Blackboard and Chalk, books, and classroom instruction. But they are adapting and managing it like a pro so that students may benefit from the new ways.

On the other hand, many instructors are forced to hunt for other employment to make ends meet. Even while well-educated parents are helping to support their children throughout the epidemic, we must recognize that other parents are illiterate and that they may feel powerless to assist their children in obtaining an education. It's not uncommon to see youngsters in India attending school merely to collect meals. It has been a huge aid to many students who couldn't bring their food to school because of the fantastic midday meal program. Many youngsters were starving to death as a result of the shutdown of their schools. Exams are often postponed or canceled, causing uncertainty among pupils and leaving little learning opportunity.

For the sake of their family's survival, the majority of school-age children engage in child labor. The financial and opportunity expenses of educating girls and transgender youngsters may have an impact on their parents. In addition to kids, low-income institutions and schools have been hit by this epidemic, leading to their closure. During the Covid-19, there are both good and terrible events taking on around us. Students and professors may communicate electronically through online classrooms, webinars, digital tests, and so on, thanks to the advancements in technology. But the sad reality is that many pupils throughout the country are unable to access it. Everything is being done to ensure the safety of the students, so that they may return to their families uninfected. When anything like this happens again in the future, we must upgrade our infrastructure and think of methods to help the next generation if we face a pandemic like this one again. We must also provide education to every kid in the pandemic. Don't go out. Ensure that you are protected.

FACTORS THAT LED THE INDIAN EDUCATION SYSTEM TO EXACERBATE

- Crisis in the Educational Management System of India.
- Unequal treatment of online pedagogy.
- Interpersonal Interaction of Student & Teacher.
- Lacking Social Skills
- Equality of Education
- jeopardizes the health and safety of the students.
- Role and Capacity of Educators.

FINLAND'S IMPECCABLE HOLDING IN THE PANDEMIC DAYS ON ITS EDUCATION SYSTEM

Schools in Finland will be closed on March 18, 2020. They successfully reopened on May 14th, 2020. Finland was able to make the switch from face-to-face instruction to distant learning and back again because of many factors. There is a predetermined response. To properly serve the well-being of children, the Finns have a stance on education and learning that frequently defies popular knowledge (such as caring less about children's standardized performance and teachers' responsibility).

Even in the era of technology-driven educational services, the Finns remain enthusiastic about face-to-face education. New or renovated twenty-first century superschools have been built or remodeled to produce excellent and highly resourced teaching and learning environments that allow instructors and students to engage face-to-face and online. Schools are no longer only places to teach and study topics, but rather a phenomenon where the full learning experience and children's development take place thanks to a combination of national, municipal, and school policies. Teachers and students work hard to ensure that the children feel secure in a calm atmosphere of mutual respect between the two groups.

For the benefit of educational exchange, Finland has built a strong teaching force and a technology infrastructure (sound broadband internet access and educational tools so that teachers can navigate different pedagogic proposals and environments). They've eliminated many of the smaller, less-resourced schools in favor of building massive superschools that can accommodate many more pupils. It's one of their core concepts to have fewer, better-resourced schools rather than a large number of underfunded ones.

Digitalization in schools was a natural progression from that seen in the workplace and home, but schools took it a step further. More time spent in front of a screen does not equate to more knowledge gained. Since everyone in Finland has access to the internet, the schools have made it a goal of theirs for everyone to learn how to utilize this technology for their benefit. They don't compel digitalization, but they ensure that all schools are equipped for instructors and students who wish to experiment with digital tools.

During the pandemic, schools and teachers were able to communicate effectively with parents and students because the Finnish model of education places a high value on education (for example, the teaching profession is one of the most highly sought-after fields of university studies by high school students).

Students' and instructors' health and well-being became increasingly important as a result of the pandemic because of the increase in digitalization, flexibility, and cooperation. So, what can we anticipate for the future? Students need more frequent formative assessments, more outdoor space, better digital skills, and more frequent formative evaluations in the near term. They also need greater long-term preparation for potential disasters.

FACTORS THAT KEPT THE EDUCATION SYSTEM OF FINLAND UNAFFECTED

- Sustaining Digital Learning as a Standard Curriculum Component in the Schools
- Distance learning worked well
- Education was enhanced through interpersonal interactions between educator, student, and their parents.
- Awareness among the student's parents.
- Safety measures were paramount for school organizations.
- Fostering the educational needs of the students.

CONCLUSION

The findings of the study state that in India because of a larger population they could not prepare well in advance for the pandemic which resulted in poor conditions in the teaching and learning process for both students and teachers. The online platform brought an advantageous edge for the student who is from well-to-do families but parallelly, it was a great deal of loss on students who couldn't afford or cope with the need of the hour which was digital learning. Which eventually brought to the table a stigma and huge loss to our education system as on average most of the students belongs to those section of society who could not match the standard of digital learning. On the other hand, Finns were ready to beat the heat of covid- 19 as Finland was able to make the switch from face-to-face instruction to distant learning and back again because of many factors. It was a predetermined response from their side to properly serve the well-being of children, the Finns have a stance on education and learning that frequently defies popular knowledge (such as caring less about children's standardized performance and teachers' responsibility). The cardinal reason behind the matching up with digital learning was the students in Finland on average were from literate and well-to-do families, furthermore, digital learning was prevalent in their Educational Culture way before India and other roughly affected nations took into force. During the pandemic, schools and teachers were able to communicate effectively with parents and students because the Finnish model of education places a high value on education - for example, the teaching profession is one of the most highly sought-after fields of university studies by high school students.

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